

Overcoming self-confidence of Islamic religious education students: The influence of personal learning model

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ABSTRACT

Research on student confidence has been done a lot, but the focus in the field of personal learning models has not been found. This study aimed to determine the strengthening of personal learning models in developing student self-confidence. A total of 688 students were recruited as research samples using questionnaires as data collection techniques, and analyzed using simple linear regression. This research found that personal learning models can significantly develop students' self-confidence in Islamic Religious Education subjects. The personal learning model used by the teacher is quite strong in overcoming students' self-confidence in learning Islamic religious education. Predictable, if the personal learning model is maximally applied by Islamic religious education teachers in learning, to be "strong" for increase the self-confidence of students in learning Islamic religious education. This study concludes that the teacher's personal learning model can develop students' self-confidence in learning Islamic religious education. The findings of this study develop students' self-confidence theories by applying personal learning models in teacher education activities. In addition, opening a discussion room is very intense for other researchers in developing the self-confidence of students in the learning of Islamic education in schools.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Self-confidence is an important thing that must be owned by students, especially in the world of education so that they get success. According to Omer [1] that student self-confidence is very useful in developing themselves, strengthening themselves, being brave in taking risks, and forming personalities always want to advance with their competence in life. Chandra, Wibowo and Sunawan [2] revealed that self-confidence is the most important basic capital in a person so that he can actualize himself. Confidence is one of the results of positive self-actualization, by having students' confidence in being able to develop their talents, interests, and potentials, so that they will become a success or what is called talent. Conversely, without self-confidence, students will tend to experience difficulties in developing their talents or potential.

Zapko, et al. [3] asserted that the teacher learning structure is very important in increasing students' fondness in learning religious education. Self-confidence is one important aspect of personality that must be possessed by everyone. Personality is very influential on the pattern of acceptance of one's social

environment. People who have personalities in accordance with what is owned by the surrounding community, then he will get good acceptance from the community [4]. Jaaffar, et al. [5] revealed that the concept of self-confidence has been widely discussed in psychology and applied research. Self-confidence as the ability of an individual to recognize his or her own ability, love towards himself/herself or an awareness of his or her own emotions. Self-confidence as feelings of well-being because of deepening positive emotions. Self-confidence is reported as an integral psychological construct that affects a student's academic performance. Possessing self-confidence means there is an expectation that a person will achieve a goal in a certain situation. The role of educational or teaching methods, such as personal model learning programs, can influence the development of an undergraduate's self-confidence.

Self-confidence is as adjustment or called a ruler, that is someone who has the ability to make plans, organize every response, be able to overcome all conflicts and solve problems. A person who lacks confidence tends to avoid communication situations, because he is afraid that others will ridicule him. When in discussion he will be more silent, when speaking he speaks not fluently. Results provide strong support for using serial simulation as a learning tool. Students were satisfied with the experience, felt confident in their performance, and felt the simulations were based on sound educational practices and were important for learning. Serial simulations and having students experience simulations more than once in consecutive years is a valuable method instruction. When conducted well, simulations can lead to increased student satisfaction and self-confidence. Someone who has self-confidence more often gets success compared to someone who has low self-confidence [6].

“The pious person will develop a positive self-concept, because a person will not be easily influenced and will have a strong sense of confidence because he believes in the word of Allah SWT which means: “Indeed, the person who is most noble among us by Allah is the most pious among you. Verily Allah is all-knowing, all-knowing”(QS. al-Hujuraat: 13).”

There are several studies on self-confidence, including Nur'aini [7] stating that the low self-confidence of Patani Students (Southern Thailand) Islamic Religious Education Study Program Faculty of Islamic Religion Riau Islamic University can be seen from some of them cheating during exams, not daring to ask lecturers, do not dare to give arguments when discussing in class and some of them are also reluctant or unwilling to interact with other Indonesian students who are in the Faculty of Islamic Religion. With the various symptoms above the solution given is to improve his self-concept. Research conducted by Komara [8] states that self-confidence is influenced by two factors, namely internal factors and external factors. Internal factors are someone's self-concept, namely one's awareness of circumstances that have a major influence on the formation of behavior. The external factor is the family environment where the family environment provides the initial formation of one's personality patterns. In addition, the formal environment or school is the second place to always practice the confidence of someone who is obtained from the family environment to friends and play groups. It is probable that one's self-confidence will also affect student motivation to be able to excel both in the academic and non-academic fields. Research by Sukenti [9] stated that implementing learning creative strategies can help overcome students' low self-esteem in asking teachers. In the process of teaching and learning often arise interactions between students and teachers, teachers and students or students and students. One form of interaction in question is when students ask the teacher. But in reality the question and answer process often experiences obstacles caused by lack of enthusiasm from students. There are many factors that cause the lack of enthusiasm of students in asking about the material delivered by the teacher. One reason is the lack of confidence of students in asking the teacher.

Although there have been found several studies on self-confidence, but the problem of a person's low self-confidence is still found in the world of education. This also happens in across all integrated junior high school in Pekanbaru, Riau, Indonesia where in the learning process students still have low self-confidence. This can be seen when the teacher tells students to come to the front of the class, but there are still some students who do not want to come to the front of the class, the reason is because of shame or other reasons. Even though these students actually know all the friends in their class clearly, but they still feel embarrassed, even though students who often speak in front of the class will get grades from the teacher as active students.

In addition, students often experience difficulties when giving their arguments or ideas while the learning process is in progress, even though the teacher always motivates students to be active in giving their arguments or ideas in the learning process. In addition, some students also often appear more aloof and often do not want to socialize with other friends. From some of the symptoms of confidence above, it is assumed to be influenced by the personal learning model. The learning model is a typical picture that a teacher has from the beginning to the end of learning [10]. While the personal learning model the development of individuals

to become whole, confident, and competent individuals [11]. The personal learning model is a model that emphasizes strong and realistic self-concepts to build productive relationships with other people and their environment by paying attention to their emotional lives [12].

The formulation of this research problem is the influence of the personal learning model on student self-confidence in Islamic religious education subjects at integrated junior high school Pekanbaru, Riau, Indonesia. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of personal learning models on student confidence in Islamic Religious Education subjects at integrated junior high school Pekanbaru, Riau, Indonesia. This research is expected to be useful to increase the body of thought for the development of science and knowledge, especially in dealing with issues related to self-confidence and to be able to provide information for related parties about the influence of personal learning models on student confidence in Islamic Religious Education subjects. In addition it is beneficial for schools in improving the quality of teaching educators, especially in the field of increasing student confidence when in the learning process. Taking wisdom in applying the model of personal learning in increasing student confidence in learning.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted with a quantitative design using an ex post facto approach to explore the development of self-confidence by strengthening the personal learning of Islamic teachers. Ex post facto research does not require the commitment of junior high school student but sees the variables studied as understood and owned by junior high school student in the Islamic religious education learning process.

This research involved 688(290 males and 398 females) students spread across all integrated junior high school in Pekanbaru (17 school), Riau, Indonesia. Sampling using Slovin formula with a margin of error of 5%. Purposive random sampling is used to determine the sample used as research respondents. To control for confounding variables in this sample, randomization was carried out. Which is the process by which people are drawn (everyone has a known and equal chance of being drawn) and their placement in any group (everyone can be assigned to any group at random).

Questionnaire is used as a data collection technique related to personal learning model and student self-confidence. The questionnaire instrument was arranged based on the theory of personal learning model and student confidence. Personal learning model instruments are arranged based on seven dimensions and student self-confidence are arranged based on five dimensions. A questionnaire instrument totaling 168 questions was tested and resulted value 85 for in a reliability. The questionnaire containing the instrument used a Likert scale used to measure the attitudes, opinions, and students' perceptions about the problem being studied. Data were analyzed using inferential to test hypotheses that have been built with regression, using SPSS version 25.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that there is an effect of personal learning model of Islamic teacher on the overcoming self-confidence of Islamic religious education student in learning. This is shown by the value of ($F = 77.041$), and the probability value (0.000) that is smaller than the value of significance (0.05) ($P < 0.05$). Based on this case, the hypothesis of research stating that there is influence of personal learning model of Islamic teacher has on the overcoming self-confidence of Islamic religious education student in learning in junior high school in Pekanbaru, Riau, Indonesia is accepted.

Table 1. Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

		ANOVA ^b				
	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1949.210	1	1949.210	77.041	.000 ^a
	Residual	2175.869	687	25.301		
	Total	4125.080	688			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Personal Learning Model
b. Dependent Variable: Self-confidence

To see how much influence the personal learning model of Islamic teacher has on the overcoming self-confidence of Islamic religious education student in learning can be seen in Table 2. Table 2 clearly illustrates the effect of personal learning model of Islamic teacher on the overcoming self-confidence of

Islamic religious education student in learning of 0.473 or 47.3%. This is indicated by the value of (R = 0.687) and the value of (R Square = 0.473).

Table 2. Model summary

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.687 ^a	.473	.466	5.030

a. Predictors: (Constant), Personal Learning Model
 b. Dependent Variable: Self-confidence

This illustrates that overcoming self-confidence of Islamic religion education student is strongly influenced by the personal learning model of Islamic teacher. Furthermore, Table 3 can be seen that if the personal learning model is improved it will give an increase in student confidence of 0.687 or 68.7%. And vice versa if the personal learning model decreases its use by teachers it will reduce the confidence of students by 68.7%.

Table 3. Coefficients

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	22.206	6.396		3.472	.001
Personal Learning Model	1.299	.148	.687	8.777	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Self-confidence

This research found that personal learning models can develop students' self-confidence. The theoretical personal learning model is a learning model that emphasizes the self-concept of each individual, makes a whole person, confident, and competent. In the results of Korhonen, Ruhalahti and Veermans's [13] research that personal learning models enable lifelong learning and make competences visible in education and professional life. Students are able to develop optimally both in aspects of motivation, achievement, self-confidence, and learning independence. The ability of teachers to develop learning methods and various strategies is very significant in developing student learning activities in the classroom. Then the teacher must have Islamic and psychological social behavior to develop quality learning activities and high competitiveness [14]. This is in accordance with the theory that the personal model is a learning model that emphasizes the development of self-concept of each individual. This includes developing individual processes and building and organizing themselves. This model focuses on strong and realistic self-concepts to build productive relationships with others and their environment.

Although there is a plethora of mobile learning studies, relatively little attention has been paid to the roles of self-management of learning and personal learning models initiative on learning outcomes. The perceived flexibility advantage and self-management of personal learning strategies not only will have a positive influence on mobile learning continuance intention and performance, but also revealed that mobile learning continuance intention will mediate the link between perceived flexibility advantage and mobile learning performance [15]. Moreover, personal learning models initiative will play a moderating role in reinforcing the positive relationship between perceived flexibility advantage and mobile learning continuance intention [16]. The personal learning model emphasizes the development of individuals to become whole, confident, and competent individuals. This model can help students to understand themselves and the goals they want to achieve. The personal learning model basically moves from the view of individual selfhood. Education and learning are activities that are deliberately carried out so that someone can understand themselves in depth, assume responsibility so that it is possible to achieve a better quality of life [17].

This personal learning model starts from a humanistic theory, which is oriented to the development of individual self. Main attention to emotional students to be able to develop productive relationships with the surrounding environment [18]. This model makes personal students who are able to form harmonious relationships and will add information effectively. The personal learning model is initially derived from the view of self-esteem, a person tries to get an education so that he tries to understand himself, be responsible for his education, and learn to develop new ones that are stronger and more creative in achieving quality life [19].

As education becomes increasingly complex, effective continuing professional learning is an important strategy to support teachers in schools. Theories of connectivism, networked learning, and connected learning underpin the model, which conceptualizes the whole experience of learning as a connected professional. The model comprises three elements: arenas of learning, teacher as learner, and personal learning strategies. Key characteristics of the experience are practices described as linking, stretching, and amplifying [20]. These practices recur in various ways across all three elements of the model. The model promotes professional learning that is active, interest-driven, and autonomous, meeting personal learning needs while being socially connected [21]. Personal learning model is oriented to self-development into individuals who have good personality qualities characterized by having stable and controlled emotions. The attention of this model is focused on the personal emotional life of individuals, so the educational process is designed to assist students in developing harmonious relationships with other individuals and their environments [22]. Kennedy's [23] research explores the question, how can connectedness form in a network of personal learning methods? Six doctoral students participated in three phases of data collection that included descriptions of written life experiences, observations of hard thinking, and in-depth interviews. The learning model that is applied has a strong correlation with motivation, learning, and their identity in learning. Their academic achievement level is getting higher, including motivation to write in mass media and academic texts.

The results of this study found that confidence was influenced by 0.473 or 47.3% by the personal learning model, while the rest 52.7% was influenced by other factors. In other studies there are also several factors that can affect self-confidence apart from the personal learning model. Self-concept was able to contribute 42.7% in increasing the confidence of Thai students in the Islamic Faculty of Islamic University of Riau Islamic University, the rest 57.3% could be influenced by factors other factors. The effective contribution of peer support by 27% on self-confidence, the rest 73% is influenced by other factors that affect self-confidence. Self-confidence and learning achievement contribute to student career planning by 52.8%, while the remaining 47.3% is influenced by other variables such as physical, psychological, and environmental. Self-confidence is very important to be increased because it is a personal characteristic of a person in which there is confidence in one's ability and is able to develop and manage him as a person who is able to solve a problem with the best situation [24]. Self-confidence arises from actions, activities, and efforts to act instead of avoiding circumstances and being passive. Trust itself is a firm belief in the heart, understanding and ability according to the heart [25]. Self-confidence is confidence in solving a problem to achieve certain goals in accordance with the actions of the situations encountered. People who have high confidence will easily socialize well, have good tolerance, be positive, and are not easily influenced by the surrounding environment [26].

Self-confidence is a shadow of thought, feelings, beliefs, and also the courage of a person to the expertise he has, which includes intellectual abilities, attitudes, feelings, physical strength, and appearance [27]. In the process of learning achievement is a proof stage of self-realization that is recognized by the teacher and fellow students. The more often successful in completing the task, the stronger the confidence in him. The opposite can happen, if repeated failures can lead to insecurity [28]. The growth of confidence starts from a competency in accordance with the phase of child development, or it can also be from the work they have. For example, someone who is good at reciting competencies, with these competencies the child will get recognition from friends in the surrounding environment [29]. Then after receiving the recognition, the child's confidence will begin to grow. The higher one's confidence, the higher the quality of competence [30].

A learning approach that is only demanding a student to do something as desired by the teacher or school, will not be able to arouse student motivation. Hope that high on students able to develop all the potential they have as mandated by Law No. 20 of 2003 Article 3 which says: "objectives national education is to develop the potential of students to become people who believe and fear God Almighty, moral noble ... "can be realized. Learning is more demanding, rather than understanding students, precisely will only produce students' fear and distrust [31]. Successful people are people who have confidence and believe in themselves. People who have a belief does not mean he does not accept fate [32]. Self-confidence is a positive attitude towards one's ability to develop positive values towards oneself or the surrounding environment. Self-confidence is one of the psychological conditions of a person that affects physical and mental activity in the learning process [33]. Confidence means the belief that we hold towards ourselves. To have a belief it requires courage, the ability to take risks, and readiness to accept all failures and disappointments [34]. A strong personality is formed through the process of how children who are in accordance with their development are able to understand their strengths and weaknesses and are confident in their abilities [35]. The students' confidence in learning can be enhanced by the use of problem-based learning methods and contextual learning [36].

Thus, the personal learning model is a crucial aspect that is able to develop students' confidence in the learning of Islamic religious education. Confidence must be developed because students increasingly

have high creativity and achievement in learning [37]. The use of a personal learning model is demanded maximally by Islamic religious education teachers so that students increasingly have the ability, creativity, and courage in learning [38]. The problem of students' self-confidence must be developed and fostered continuously by the teacher in learning, because it has a big impact on the character and personality of students in the future, in the world of work, and old age.

4. CONCLUSION

Personal learning models can significantly develop students' confidence in Islamic Religious Education subjects. The personal learning model used by the teacher is quite strong in overcoming students' confidence in learning Islamic religious education in the world of education. Predictable, if the personal learning model is maximally applied by Islamic religious education teachers in learning, then it is predicted to be "strong (.687)" to increase the confidence of students in learning Islamic religious education. This study concluded that the teacher's personal learning model can develop students' confidence in learning Islamic religious education. The findings of this study develop students' self-confidence theories by applying personal learning models in teacher education activities.

Since there are many students who have the confidence of students in learning, it is recommended that the Department of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia conduct training for teachers on the use of personal learning models so as to give birth to students who are confident. In addition, opening a discussion room is very intense for other researchers in developing the confidence of students in the education of Islamic education in schools.

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